

POTENTIAL POSITIONING OF MERLIN PROJECT

Reference information	New or existing standard	Deadline for adoption by the ESOs
1. European standard(s) on the process and criteria to evaluate the recyclability of plastic packaging.	New	2 August 2025
2. European standard(s) on the definitions and principles for design-for-recycling of plastic packaging.	New	2 August 2025
3. European standardisation deliverables on design-for-recycling guidelines for plastic packaging products: polyolefins flexibles; polystyrene (PS) cups, trays and dairy packaging; polyolefins rigids; polyethylene terephthalate (PET) beverage bottles; PET trays; expanded polystyrene (EPS) packaging.	New	2 August 2025
8. European standardisation deliverable(s) on quality grades for sorted plastics wastes: HDPE, LDPE, PP, PET, PVC, PS, EPS.	New	2 August 2025
1. EN 15347:2007 Plastics – Recycled plastics – Characterisation of plastics wastes.	Existing	2 August 2025
3. EN 15344:2021 Plastics – Recycled Plastics – Characterisation of polyethylene (PE) recyclates.	Existing	2 August 2025
4. EN 15345:2007 Plastics – Recycled Plastics – Characterisation of polypropylene (PP) recyclates.	Existing	2 August 2025
6. EN 15348:2014 Plastics - Recycled plastics - Characterisation of poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) recyclates.	Existing	2 August 2025